

A SYNTHESIS OF 2-BENZOYL-4-ETHYLRESORCINOL

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A synthesis of 2-benzoyl-4-ethyl resorcinol has been described

It is well known that the Fries migration is widely employed for the preparation of phenolic ketones. In recent years, the migration has been extended to the esters of hydroxycoumarins. It gives rise to hydroxy-acyl-coumarins, which, on elimination of the pyrone ring, yield otherwise difficultly accessible 2-acyl-resorcinols. Several 2-acyl-resorcinols have thus been prepared by Limaye and his co-workers (*Ber.*, 1932, 65, 375; 1934, 67, 12; *Rasayanam*, 1937, 80; 1938, 141; 1939, 191 *et seq.*)

In connection with other work, 2-benzoyl-4-ethylresorcinol was required for purposes of comparison; since it was not known, we have employed the above method and synthesised it from 4-ethylresorcinol (I), which under the customary conditions of the Pechmann reaction, yields 7-hydroxy-6-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin (II), the benzoyl ester (III) of which, on being subjected to the Fries migration gives 7-hydroxy-6-ethyl-8-benzoyl-4-methylcoumarin (IV). It is hydrolysed by alkali and on acidification, 2-benzoyl-4-ethylresorcinol (V) is obtained. It gives deep colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution and dissolves in alkali giving a yellow solution. Further, it easily undergoes the Pechmann condensation with ethyl acetoacetate yielding the original coumarin (IV), a reaction characteristic of 2-acyl-resorcinols.

EXPERIMENTAL

7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-6-ethylcoumarin (II) required in this work was prepared by the Pechmann condensation of 4-ethylresorcinol with ethyl acetoacetate. Phosphorus oxychloride as the condensing agent was found to give the best yields, m.p. 217°. Shah and Samant (M.Sc. thesis, Bom. Univ., 1935) give m.p. 211-12°; Limaye (*Rasayanam*, 1941, 201) gives m.p. 213°; Chakravarti and Chakravarti (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 149) give m.p. 210°.

7-Benzoyloxy-4-methyl-6-ethylcoumarin (III) was prepared by benzoyl chloride-pyridine method, m.p. 155°.

Fries migration of (III): *Formation of 7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-6-ethyl-8-benzoylcoumarin* (IV).—The benzoyloxy derivative (1 mol.) was intimately mixed with powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (3.3 mols.) and heated in an oil-bath at 150-160° for nearly 2 hours. Hydrochloric acid fumes were evolved and the mixture melted and formed a yellow paste. It was cooled, ice and hydrochloric acid added; the solid obtained collected, washed and crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 160-61°. It gives a deep violet colour with alcoholic ferric chloride and dissolves in alkali to a yellow non-fluorescent solution.

2-Benzoyl-4-ethylresorcinol (V).—The product (IV, 5 g.) was refluxed with alkali solution (20% ; 30 c.c.) for 2-2½ hours and cooled. It was then acidified and the separated solid collected, washed with water and crystallised from acetic acid as yellow needles, m.p. 125-26°, yield 2 g. (Found : C, 74.2 ; H, 5.9. $C_{15}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 74.4 ; H, 5.8 per cent). It easily dissolves in methyl and ethyl alcohols, ether, acetone and acetic acid, and less so in benzene, chloroform and petrol ethers.

The *dimethyl ether*, prepared by dimethyl sulphate, crystallised from methanol as prisms, m.p. 60°. (Found : C, 75.4 ; H, 6.6 ; $C_{17}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 75.6 ; H, 6.7 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative melts at 65° ; the *benzoyl* derivative melts at 60°.

Pechmann condensation.—The resorcinol (V, 1 g.) was mixed with ethyl acetoacetate (1 g.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (5 c.c.) and the mixture kept for 24 hours. It was then poured into cold water and the solid obtained crystallised from acetic acid as yellow needles, m.p. 160° ; mixed m.p. with an authentic sample (IV) remained unchanged.

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